

Evaluation of Human Body Scattering in Near and Far Field by Iterative Physical Optics for mmWave Sensing Applications

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Abstract—Millimeter-wave radar-based human body sensing requires for precise modeling of the backscattered field. This article presents an Iterative Physical Optics model designed for evaluating the near field backscattering of lossy dielectric target. The model is first validated by millimeter wave measurement in anechoic chamber and applied to simplified human body, in order to examine the impact that proximity to the target can have on the electromagnetic response.

Index Terms—Near field backscattering, Millimeter wave radar, Radar Cross Section (RCS), Human body.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of millimeter wave (mmWave) sensing is nowadays driven by advancements in radar sensors technology. Due to its wide bandwidth and short wavelength, mmWave backscattering sensing is considered as one of the most promising sensing technologies. Hence, mmWave radars are becoming key enablers for a wide range of sensing applications, extending far beyond traditional radar use cases, including autonomous vehicles, smart homes, and industrial applications. For example, in autonomous vehicles, mmWave radars are aimed at obstacle detection and motion estimation, taking advantage of their ability to detect humans and the low cost of deploying devices [1]. This technology is being applied in various human sensing scenarios, such as tracking, motion recognition, biometric monitoring, and imaging [2]. Additionally, the use of backscattering sensing is envisioned for future 6G networks and Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) [3]. In these applications, the human body is often the target being sensed. In the past, human body scattering has been experimentally characterized [4], [5] under very specific conditions, without considering the actual distance between the target and the antenna. However, in most application scenarios, the radar sensor is often positioned at a close distance where the entire body can be perceived as an extended target. Given the short wavelength, the antenna is in the near zone of the backscattered field. This raises the challenge of accurately modeling the backscattering of a lossy dielectric target, while considering both near and far field conditions based on the intended application.

Iterative physical optics (IPO) is a fast and robust electromagnetic model that simplifies complex interactions by focusing on the induced surface currents on the object. It can accurately describe the backscattering from target with complex shape or cavities. It has been extended to dielectric and lossy materials [6] and physical optics has been applied in human related scenario [7]. This method offers a relatively accurate estimation of backscatter for complex geometries without the need to resolve every small field interaction, making the analysis more manageable and computationally efficient. However, despite its effectiveness, IPO may require adjustments or complementary methods, such as edge effects through Physical Theory of Diffraction (PTD) [8] or Fast Far Field Approximation (FaFFA) [9] to accelerate the model. Models based on physical optics for human body in indoor propagation exists like in [10], the goal of this article is to present the capabilities of an IPO near-field model intended for applications in human sensing scenarios. Sec. II introduces the model, followed by its validation through measurements of a sample of human body equivalent dielectric (Sec. III). Once the model is validated through measurements, in Sec. IV the developed tool is applied to a full-body mannequin in order to evaluate its radar cross section (RCS) in both the near and the far field.

II. IPO BASED BACKSCATTERING MODEL

To apply the IPO method for dielectric and lossy materials, the induced electric and magnetic currents on the surface of the object are calculated to determine the scattered field. The electric and magnetic currents are defined as follows [6] :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J} &= \left((1 - \Gamma_{\perp}) \mathbf{H}_{inc}^{\perp} + (1 - \Gamma_{\parallel}) \mathbf{H}_{inc}^{\parallel} \right) \wedge \hat{\mathbf{n}} \\ \mathbf{M} &= \left((1 - \Gamma_{\perp}) \mathbf{E}_{inc}^{\perp} + (1 - \Gamma_{\parallel}) \mathbf{E}_{inc}^{\parallel} \right) \wedge \hat{\mathbf{n}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where Γ_{\perp} and Γ_{\parallel} represents the Fresnel coefficients and \mathbf{E}_{inc} and \mathbf{H}_{inc} represents the incident fields. The magnetic field

Fig. 1: IPO representation for iteration $k+1$

backscattered in near field by a surface m of size s can be written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_{scat}^{(m)} = \iint_s \left[-\frac{(j\beta_i R_r + 1)}{R_r} \left(\mathbf{J}^{(m)} \wedge \hat{\mathbf{R}}_r \right) + \frac{1}{\eta_i} \frac{-j\beta_i R_r + (\beta_i R_r)^2}{j\beta_i R_r^2} \left(\mathbf{M}^{(m)} \right) + \frac{1}{\eta_i} \frac{-j3\beta_i R_r + (\beta_i R_r)^2}{j\beta_i R_r^2} \left(\mathbf{M}^{(m)} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{R}}_r \right) \hat{\mathbf{R}}_r \right] \frac{e^{-j\beta_i (R_r)}}{4\pi R_r} ds \quad (2)$$

And analogously for the electric field. β_i and η_i represents the wave vector and the impedance of the corresponding material. $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_r$ is the distance vector to the receiver.

The target is divided into triangular facets and these facets are represented as flat meshes with a size small enough to be treated with a plane wave illumination from all the other radiating elements. By employing physical shadowing, the currents flowing through the illuminated surfaces are iteratively calculated to account for the several interactions between the sub-parts of the target. The Fig. 1 represents the behavior of the IPO model. On the sub-surface n , the currents at iteration $k+1$ will be equal to the sum of the current from all the other sub-surfaces:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}^{(k+1,n)} &= \sum_{m=1, m \neq n} U^{(m \rightarrow n)} \mathbf{J}^{(k+1, m \rightarrow n)} \\ \mathbf{M}^{(k+1,n)} &= \sum_{m=1, m \neq n} U^{(m \rightarrow n)} \mathbf{M}^{(k+1, m \rightarrow n)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The function $U^{(n \rightarrow m)}$ is a function which is beforehand defined to handle physical optics shadowing, and $\mathbf{J}^{(k+1, m \rightarrow n)}$ refers to the currents generated on surface n by the fields scattered by the surface m . For the first iteration, the incident fields are defined based on the transmitter radiation.

III. MODEL VALIDATION

To validate the accuracy of the model and its capabilities in addressing human sensing scenarios, measurements were made using a lossy dielectric cube with a side length of 5.6 cm. The cube is made of lossy silicone which can emulate the human body electromagnetic properties and is compliant to

CTIA recommendations for OTA testing [11]. The choice of this geometry instead of a complete human body shape aims to validate the model in a canonical case, before applying it to model complex shapes. Measurements were performed by means of Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) in an anechoic chamber with a distance of 50 cm between the target and the antennas. The target was placed on a rotative support to characterize the results in scenarios where the receiving antenna is not in the specular direction. The Fig.2 shows the measurement setup. The antennas used are horns operating from 22 GHz to 33 GHz. At these frequencies, the corresponding cube's relative permittivity ranges to 20 to 21 and the conductivity ranges to $4.11S.m^{-1}$ to $5.7S.m^{-1}$. In this scenario, the receiving antenna is in the near field of the backscattering target, meaning that precise positioning of all the scenario's elements is necessary to obtain accurate measurements. Based on the Fraunhofer criterion, the far field distance at 33 GHz is around 80 cm. The precise positioning was achieved using a cross-line laser, positioners and a laser rangefinder. A prior measurement was performed without the target to remove the support and the anechoic chamber responses. The support was chosen as a cone foam to reduce the possible interactions between the target and the support.

The measurements were performed with a 5° step rotation. During post-processing, an error of 1° was identified in target alignment. This indicates that the model needs to be set with a 5° step rotation centered at 1° instead of 0° . To accurately describe the backscattering of the target, the square modulus of the round-trip transfer function is employed. It is calculated as follows:

$$|\mathcal{H}(f)|^2 = \frac{1}{P_{TX}} \frac{c^2}{f^2 \eta_0} \frac{|\mathbf{E}_{RX}(f) \wedge \mathbf{H}_{RX}^*(f)|}{2} \quad (4)$$

Where P_{TX} is the transmitted power, c the celerity of light, $\mathbf{E}_{RX}(f)$ and $\mathbf{H}_{RX}(f)$ refers to the fields perceived by the antenna. The complex gain of the antenna is modeled with Finite Integration Technique (FIT) with the software CST MWS®.

The results in Fig. 2 exhibit an excellent agreement between the model and the measurements. The shift of less than 1 dB could be attributed to the precision of the measurements or the implementation of the antennas. In this scenario, the penetrated power accounted for approximately 60% of the response as evanescent fields resulting from the cube's conductivity.

IV. HUMAN BODY BACKSCATTERING

To model the backscattering of the human body, the first approximation is to use the skin model and shape as a simplified dielectric layer with a homogeneous surface, accounting for reflections and absorption. In this article a 1.83 m mannequin STL file presented in Fig. 3 is used to describe the scattering characteristics of human body. To accurately apply IPO to curved targets, the surface elements must be sufficiently small to ensure that the local curvature can be approximated as planar, allowing for more precise scattering calculations [12].

Fig. 2: Backscattering measurement setup (a). Results of the backscattering in the near field for different azimuthal angles (b): model (continuous line) vs. measurement (dashed line).

Fig. 3: Human body mannequin geometry and initial meshing with antenna positioning

A. Round Trip Transfer Function

Here we evaluated the scattering field of the human body at 50 cm (corresponding to near field). We evaluate the bistatic backscattering in three incident directions $\phi_{inc} = (0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ)$, corresponding to the three TX position TX1, TX2, TX3 in Fig. 3.

In Fig. 4 we show the normalized scattered field over the body, together with obtained transfer function for the TX1 and the TX3 and receiver at $\phi = 0^\circ$. In the TX1 position the two main scatterers parts are the top of the torso and the chin. In TX3 case where the transmitter is on the left side of the target and the receiver is in front. As shown in Fig. 4c, due to the complex geometry, all the sub-surfaces of the left part of the body are not scattering towards the receiver. The main transmitting parts are the neck and the shoulder. The round trip transfer function clearly demonstrates the idea that there are two main bounces.

Fig. 4: Normalized backscattered field, both antenna in front (a). Round trip transfer function of the scenario 1 (b). Normalized backscattered field TX on the side, RX on the front (c). Round trip transfer function of the scenario 2 (d).

B. Near Field RCS

In order to compare measurements at several distances, the near field radar cross section (RCS) is employed [13]. This metric has been chosen, instead of the full round trip transfer function in Sec. III, in order to fairly compare the scattering at different distances. Near field RCS is defined as:

$$\sigma_{NF} = 4\pi R_r^2 \frac{|\mathbf{E}_{scat} \wedge \mathbf{H}_{scat}|}{|\mathbf{E}_{inc} \wedge \mathbf{H}_{inc}|} \quad (5)$$

In the RCS estimation we considered the same illumination provided by horn antennas in measurement and compensated the antenna gain.

Fig. 5 shows the RCS patterns for the three different TX positions highlighted in Fig. 5d, averaged over the 22 GHz-33 GHz band for two distances, 50 cm and 10 m. For TX1, the RCS is maximize for the monostatic case and the -3 dB beamwidth is around 120° for the 10 m measurement and around 100° for the 50 cm scenario. In this case, the evolution of the RCS is similar for both distances. For TX2, the diagram is not symmetrical due to the arrival angle. Interestingly, the human body's monostatic case still shows the highest response at 50 cm. The "flat" part of the torso does not represent the main scattering part. For TX3 where the transmitter is on the left side of the target, the RCS is maximized in the monostatic case too. As can be seen, in the 10 m case, the RCS is higher than at 50 cm. This is mainly due to the larger illuminated area at greater distances, which increases the scattering surface. The results show that up to 20 dB difference can be found in the RCS at different distances, illustrating the importance of taking

Fig. 5: Human body bistatic RCS at 50 cm and 10 m for three different incident angles corresponding to TX1 (a), TX2 (b), TX3 (c). Human body and antenna positioning (d).

care of near field effect. To properly demonstrate the evolution of the RCS along distance, we evaluated the monostatic RCS of the torso from 50 cm to 50 m. The RCS plotted in Fig. 6 exhibits an evolution that converges to ≈ 10 dBsm for far field distances. It is important to note that, with respect to experimental results in the literature [4], this result highlights the differences given by the proximity of the target from the antenna.

Fig. 6: Evolution of human body monostatic RCS along distance

V. CONCLUSION

In this work we presented an Iterative Physical Optics (IPO) model for near-field backscattering of lossy dielectric targets. The IPO model was validated through measurements in anechoic chambers of a cubic sample of lossy material mimicking the human body dielectric constant. The IPO

model was applied to evaluate the backscattering of the body, highlighting the differences in terms of RCS according to the near/far field condition. A variation up to 20 dB was found according to the distance in a frequency range from 22 to 33 GHz. The model and results are of practical interest for radar-based sensing applications aimed at the detection of human bodies .

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Kong, C. Huang, J. Yu, and X. Shen, "A Survey of mmWave Radar-Based Sensing in Autonomous Vehicles, Smart Homes and Industry," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, pp. 1–1, 2024.
- [2] T. Wu, T. S. Rappaport, and C. M. Collins, "The human body and millimeter-wave wireless communication systems: Interactions and implications," in *2015 IEEE international conference on communications (ICC)*, pp. 2423–2429, IEEE, 2015.
- [3] E. C. Strinati, , and *et al.*, "Distributed Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications: The 6G-DISAC Approach," in *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications 6G Summit (EuCNC6G Summit)*, pp. 392–397, 2024.
- [4] E. Schubert, M. Kunert, W. Menzel, J. Fortuny-Guasch, and J.-M. Chareau, "Human RCS measurements and dummy requirements for the assessment of radar based active pedestrian safety systems," in *2013 14th International Radar Symposium (IRS)*, vol. 2, pp. 752–757, 2013.
- [5] N. A. Abbasi, A. F. Molisch, and J. C. Zhang, "Measurement of directionally resolved radar cross section of human body for 140 and 220 GHz bands," in *2020 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshops (WCNCW)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 2020.
- [6] J. G. Meana, J. Á. Martínez-Lorenzo, F. Las-Heras, and C. Rappaport, "Wave scattering by dielectric and lossy materials using the modified equivalent current approximation (meca)," *IEEE transactions on antennas and propagation*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 3757–3761, 2010.
- [7] L. Corucci, E. Giusti, M. Martorella, and F. Berizzi, "Near field physical optics modelling for concealed weapon detection," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 6052–6057, 2012.
- [8] P. Y. Ufimtsev, *Fundamentals of the physical theory of diffraction*. John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [9] C.-C. Lu and W. C. Chew, "Fast far-field approximation for calculating the RCS of large objects," *Microwave and optical technology letters*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 238–241, 1995.
- [10] F. Mokhtari-Koushyar and A. A. Shishegar, "Scattering analysis of human body modeled by nurbs surfaces in mm-wave band," in *2014 Third Conference on Millimeter-Wave and Terahertz Technologies (MMWATT)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 2014.
- [11] CTIA, "Test Plan for Wireless Device Over-the-Air Performance, Version 3.8.2," 2019.
- [12] C. Bourlier, G. Kubické, and P. Pouliguen, "Accelerated computation of the physical optics approximation for near-field single-and double-bounces backscattering," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 7518–7527, 2019.
- [13] P. Pouliguen, R. Hémon, C. Bourlier, J.-F. Damiens, and J. Saillard, "Analytical formulae for radar cross section of flat plates in near field and normal incidence," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research B*, vol. 9, pp. 263–279, 2008.